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Author	Prof. Declan Bolton																							
Other contributors	Prof. Annemarie Kaesbohrer, Dr. Rosangela Tozzoli, Dr. Nadia Boisen, Dr. Flemming Scheutz, Dr. Hugo Guedes, Dr. Mónica Oleastro, Dr. Pikka Jokelainen, Dr. Karin Troell, Dr. Tryntsje Cuperus, Dr. Leonor Silveira, Dr. Miranda Kirchner, Catarina Flink, Dr. Gro Johannessen, Dr. Angela Pista, Dr. Angela van Hoeck, Dr. Robert Soderlund, Dr. C. Rune Stensvold, Dr. Jacinto Gomes & Dr. Marco Lalle.																							
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**Technical Report:
Data management & harmonised reporting of Shiga toxin-producing *Escherichia coli* (STEC), Enterotoxigenic *Escherichia coli* (ETEC), *Cryptosporidium* and antimicrobial resistance (AMR) in *Salmonella* and *Campylobacter* spp. in the European Union**

This is a public deliverable of One Health EJP Joint Research Project, Integrative Action-2.2, OH-HARMONY-CAP: One Health Harmonisation of Protocols for the Detection of Foodborne Pathogens and AMR Determinants.

<https://onehealthjep.eu/jip-oh-harmony-cap/>

OH-Harmony-Cap is a 3 year project which aims to collect information on current capabilities, capacities and interoperability at both the National Reference Laboratory (NRL) and the primary diagnostic level. The quantitative description of current and best practices and the development of harmonised protocols will identify and possibly close the gaps and support future studies of how best to detect and characterise foodborne pathogens across the One Health sectors. OH-Harmony-Cap Consortium comprises 18 One Health EJP partners across 14 countries.

Summary

This report describes the currently used data management and reporting systems for public health data, specifically Shiga toxin-producing *Escherichia coli* (STEC), Enterotoxigenic *Escherichia coli* (ETEC), *Cryptosporidium* and antimicrobial resistance (AMR) in *Salmonella* and *Campylobacter* spp., in the European Union. Inefficiencies and the loss of key data required to support the work of EFSA and other key stakeholders in food safety policy development are identified and discussed. Finally, solutions in the form of 3 recommendations are proposed including hardware and software harmonisation, reporting requirements and lost data, and the development of a central data hub. If implemented, better use could be made of the valuable data being generated in the many laboratories testing human, animal, food, feed and environmental isolates throughout the EU to the benefit of many stakeholders including European citizens.

1. Introduction

An efficient and effective public health surveillance system starts with the application of accredited and harmonised testing methods. Isolate characterisation also using accredited or peer reviewed methods is essential to provide the data on genotypes, antimicrobial resistance (AMR), virulence genes, etc. required for effective therapeutic treatment, epidemiological investigation and to supply the data for risk assessment, which underpins food safety policy development. Data management and communication is currently not considered a priority for many laboratories testing human, animal, food, feed and environmental isolates throughout the European Union. Moreover, data that is reported uses a linear model where a laboratory reports to a regional or national laboratory, which in turn sends the data to European Food Safety Authority (EFSA) or European Centre for Disease Prevention and Control (ECDC). As this data is usually the minimum required by law, the majority of data generated in the EU microbiology laboratory testing systems is lost and cannot be used to provide the scientific basis for the work done by EFSA and others.

Open science is a policy priority for the European Commission and the standard method of working under the research and innovation funding programmes as it improves the quality, efficiency and responsiveness of research (Open Science - European Commission). It is the EU's ambition that data should be FAIR (Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability and Reusability).

The objective of this report is to start the process of addressing ineffective data storage and transfer from the microbiology laboratory testing networks in the EU by identifying, discussing and proposing solutions based on harmonised data management and communication.

2. Currently used data management systems in Europe

To better understand the issues around data management and reporting, a questionnaire based survey was undertaken targeting European public health, veterinary and food testing institutions and National Reference Laboratories, accessed via the European Union Reference Laboratory (EURL), the EFSA Zoonoses networks and the ECDC Food and Waterborne diseases network, among others. Five questions were asked, specifically focused on STEC, ETEC, *Cryptosporidium* and AMR in *Salmonella* and *Campylobacter* as follows:

1. Do you have a specific system for data management / storing data?
2. Do you store information about the sample?
3. If so, in which way (paper, electronic, etc.)?
4. Do you report the results to a regional or national competent authority regularly?
5. Do you report testing results to ECDC or EFSA?

The results of this survey are provided in Table 1. There were 49 STEC testing laboratory respondents of which 45 have a dedicated data storage system, 47 store information about the sample (34 using electronic, 0 paper only and 13 a combination of both). These data are communicated regionally (1), nationally (15), both (10), neither (5) and to EFSA (7), ECDC (7), both (0) and neither (19). The figures for the ETEC laboratories were 19 (respondents), 16 (dedicated data management system), 17 (store sample information), 11 (electronic), 0 (paper), 4 (both), 1 (reporting regionally), 7 (nationally), 3 (both), 1 (EFSA) and 2 (ECDC). The corresponding figures for the laboratories testing for the *Cryptosporidium* were 44, 40, 40, 34, 0, 6, 3, 20, 1, 1, 0 and 0 and for AMR in *Salmonella* and *Campylobacter* were 34, 32, 34, 27, 0, 7, 1, 17, 2, 10, 6 and 1, respectively.

Thus, of those laboratories that took part in the survey, 13 do not have a specific system for data storage/management, 45 do not report their results regionally or nationally while 93 do not report directly to EFSA or ECDC. While it is possible that at least some of these 93 laboratories report to regional or national authorities, this finding, taken in conjunction with the 45 laboratories that do not report within their country, suggests that much of the data generated within the EU is not collected and stored centrally and therefore not available to inform policy, etc.

Table 1. The data management and communication practices in laboratories testing for STEC, ETEC, *Cryptosporidium* and AMR in *Salmonella* and *Campylobacter*.

Target	n	Q1: Do you have a specific system for data management / storing data?		Q2: Do you store information about the sample?		Q3: If so, in which way (electronic, paper etc.)?			Q4: Do you report the results to a regional or national competent authority regularly?				Q5: Do you report testing results to ECDC or EFSA?			
		Yes	No	Yes	No	E	P	E&P	R	N	Both	Neither	EFSA	ECDC	Both	Neither
STEC	49	45	4	47	2	34	0	13	1	15	10	5	7	7	0	19
ETEC	19	16	3	17	2	11	1	4	1	7	3	8	1	2	0	16
Crypto	44	40	4	40	4	34	0	6	3	20	1	19	1	0	0	43
AMR	34	32	2	34	0	27	0	7	1	17	2	13	10	6	1	15
Total	146	133	13	138	8	106	1	30	6	59	16	45	19	15	1	93

n = number of laboratories; E = electronic; P = paper; R = regional; N = national; Crypto = *Cryptosporidium*; AMR = antimicrobial resistance

A second questionnaire was subsequently undertaken targetting the same laboratories as before, with eight providing responses. This was designed to obtain specific information on the types of hardware and software used to store, manage and analyse data and communicate the results to relevant stakeholders (results shown in Table 2) and the types of hardware and software used to store, manage and analyse WGS data and communicate the results to a regional, national or European agencies (results shown in Table 3).

A range of different hardware is used to store sample information, including a personal computer (PC), local network data storage, own server (with backup), centralised server or using a large-scale infrastructure build on NetApp systems which is accessed through software and primarily stored as Structured Query Language (SQL) databases. The software used to store sample information includes: MS Office (Excel for laboratory results and metadata or Access databases), LIMS, VETLIMS, KLIMS, SeqSphere, LabVantage, internal LIS from Info Solutions (SmiLab) for sample data, PDF files, Power-BI, CLC genomic workbench, File maker and local laboratory information system (JUNDA).

Hardware is used to store the description of the laboratory methods used including localised computers/local network/hard drives, SQL server SSI, network data storage, centralized server with back-up and cloud based storage. The software used for methods storage includes MS Office, Access frontend to SQL database, Documentum, LabVantage, Live-Link, JUNDA and Centuri information management system in accordance with ISO-standards for the QA management and control within the agency. Code-based analysis is additionally maintained, developed and operated through a git based system that lets the authors and software developers work together.

The hardware used to store results includes PC/hard drive, network data storage local or centralized server with back-up and the corresponding software includes MS Office/Excel/Access, Labware, Ridom SeqSphere, a local laboratory information system (JUNDA) LIMS as well as specialised software such as LabVantage, Internal LIS (SmiLab from Info solutions) and SQL databases with PowerBI visualisation' SmiLab, SmiNet, Epicenter/TBeXIST, Bionumerics, Filemaker and CLC genomic workbench.

The hardware used to store WGS data includes the local server with back-up and external hard drives, external HDD or integrated NFS disks, centralised storage built on NetApp with optional StorageGrid and well as in the Cloud. These were used with a range of software including Labware, Ridom SeqSphere, Excel, as uBAM file, LIMS, CLC and Linux based OS. The bioinformatics software used included Applied Math, Bionumerics, (*Salmonella* and *E. coli*, virulence genes, AMR determinants, MLST, serotypes, among others), Galaxy (*E. coli*, virulence genes, AMR determinants, MLST, among others), Enterobase (genomes download),

Table 2. The types of hardware and software used to store, manage and analyse data and communicate the results to relevant stakeholders

Respondent	Type of samples tested	Sample information (sample type, description & metadata)		Methods (detection, isolation, confirmation, characterisation) information		Results (bacterial counts, identity of isolates, typing, AMR, virulence genes)	
		<i>What hardware do you use to store sample information?</i>	<i>What software do you use to store sample information?</i>	<i>What hardware do you use to store methods information?</i>	<i>What software do you use to store methods information?</i>	<i>What hardware do you use to store results?</i>	<i>What software do you use to store results?</i>
1	Feed, food, human, veterinary & environmental	SQL server SSI	LIMS, VETLIMS, printouts	SQL server SSI	Access frontend to SQL database	Server	Server
2	Human, veterinary or environmental	Hard drive, Network data storage	MS Office, KLIMS	Hard drive, Network data storage	MS Office	Hard drive, Network data storage	MS Office
3	Human	Centralized Server at NHN	Labware (LIMS), Ridom SeqSphere+ (WGS and metadata) and Excel (lab results and metadata)	Centralized Server at NHN	Documentum	Centralized Server at NHN	Labware, Ridom SeqSphere, Excel
4	Food	Server with back-up	Excel, Bionumerics (not so much anymore), SeqSphere (recently purchased), LabVantage	Server with back-up	Excel, LabVantage	Server with back-up	Excel, LabVantage
5	Food, Human, Environmental	Large-scale infrastructure for storage and backup build on NetApp systems. This in turn is accessed through software (and primarily stored as sql databases).	Internal LIS from Info Solutions (SmiLab) for sample data, NGS data is stored within the Torrent Suite LIMS solution, additional data (results from bioinfo analysis etc) is stored within sql	Centralised infrastructure Localized Computers	Centuri information management system in accordance with ISO-stadards for the QA management and control	Centralised infrastructure Localized Computer, Prints (paper)	Internal LIS (SmiLab from Info solutions) and sql databases with PowerBI visualisation Excel, Access, Power-BI

		Computer, paper Computer/server/paper request form	databases and visualised using PowerBI. PDF-files,, Access, Power-BI CLC genomic workbench EpiBact (Access database) Filemaker BioNumerics		within the agency. Code-based analysis is additionally maintained and Dev/Ops:ed through a git based system with CI/CD		SmiLab, SmiNet, Epicenter/TBeXIST, Excel Bionumerics Filemaker CLC genomic workbench
6	Veterinary	Server	LIMS based sample manager	Cloud based storage	Live-Link	Server	LIMS based sample manager
7	Feed, food, human, veterinary and environmental	Local network data storage	Local laboratory information system (JUNDA)	Local network data storage	Local laboratory information system (JUNDA)	Local network data storage	Local laboratory information system (JUNDA)
8	Feed, food, human, veterinary or environmental): all (but mainly food/animal/environmental)	Internal server	MS Excel, MS OneNote	Internal server capacity .c.w. server capacity from SURF SARA (https://userinfo.surfsara.nl/)	MS Excel, MS Word, MS OneNote, iDocuments (webbased quality management program iProva)	: Internal server capacity i.c.w. server capacity from SURF SARA (https://userinfo.surfsara.nl/)	MS Excel, MS OneNote, BioNumerics

Table 3. The types of hardware and software used to store, manage and analyse WGS data and communicate the results to a regional, national or European agency

	WGS data				Communication
Respondent	What hardware do you use to store WGS data?	What software do you use to store WGS data?	What bioinformatics software do you routinely use and to test for what?	Do you upload your WGS data to a public / other database? (if 'yes' please provide a link)	How do you communicate your results to a regional, national or European agency (EFSA or ECDC)?
1	Server Parasitology does not do WGS but they produce NGS-based data, stored on a designated server, and data outputs are available on encrypted drives.	Server	Applied Math, Bionumerics. Internal pipelines (serotype/serogroup: <i>Salmonella</i> , <i>E.coli</i> / <i>Shigella</i> , <i>Listeria</i> , <i>Yersinia</i> ; BION for microbiome analysis)	European Nucleotide Archive (ENA)	ECDC: annual reports, Epinyt, Tessa, OIE
2	External HDD or Integrated NFS Disks.	None	CGE (<i>Salmonella</i> and <i>E. coli</i> , virulence genes, AMR determinants, MLST, serotypes, among others), Galaxy (<i>E. coli</i> , virulence genes, AMR determinants, MLST, among others), Enterobase (genomes download), pubMLST (<i>Campylobacter</i> and <i>Salmonella</i> , MLST)	Yes, Science Data (https://sciencedata.dk/), CERBERUS (https://sikkerftp.ssi.dk/login), ARIES (https://w3.iss.it/site/aries/), ECDC database	Exchange of files (e.g. Excel files).
3	Centralized Server at NHN	Labware, Ridom SeqSphere, Excel	Ridom SeqSphere+: MLST, cgMLST, SeqSero (<i>Salmonella</i>), internal pipelines (serotype/serogroup: <i>E.coli</i> / <i>Shigella</i> , <i>Listeria</i> , <i>Yersinia</i>)	No	ECDC: annual reports, EpiPulse

4	Server with back-up and external hard drives	Excel, SeqSphere	Own developed system in Linux called BacIL that uses free software's (for downsampling, trimming, assembly, quality check, contamination check, characterization, AMR and SNP-typing for <i>L. monocytogenes</i> , STEC, <i>Campylobacter</i> and <i>Salmonella</i> . SeqSphere (recently purchased) Aries (Galaxy based from ISS EURL <i>E. coli</i>) for STEC (trimming, assembly, quality check, contamination check, characterization, and typing. DTU Center for Genomic Epidemiology (characterization, typing)	Sporadically – ENA European Nucleotide Archive https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/home EFSA database	National and regional – national agencies have tight collaboration in outbreak situations or in projects. We mostly communicate the results in closed web-based workspaces. The data is sent in cloud-based or ftp-based systems. European agencies – via ftp-based systems or other
5	Centralised storage built on NetApp with optional StorageGrid. Computer OwnCloud	Data is stored as uBAM files. LIMS manages data accessibility and audit trail. CLC, windows	BactTyper as well as some additional tools. BactTyper is a naïve java application running on primarily bacterial WGS data, processing and managing a pipeline involving QC, Assembly, Classification and reporting. Reporting is then ingested into sql database for downstream access. visualization through SNPAnalyzer (in-house design, javabased) CLC Genomic work benchBionumerics NCBI BLAST (online) pubMLST (online) Pasteur MLST(online)	Occasionally for studies or specific internationally connected outbreaks. ENA, SRA (NCBI), EpiPulse	SmiLab (national), SmiNet (National), EPIS-ELDSNet/EpiPulse (EU), TESSy, EpiELDSnet
6	Cloud based storage	Linux based OS used for storage and analysis of WGS data.	In-House SeqFinder – to detect AMR genes, virulence, OH antigens Abriicate– to detect AMR genes, virulence, OH antigens Spades, Unicycler – Assemble data Srst2- MLST types Snippy- SNP distances. RaxML – phylogenetic trees BRIG – plasmid genome analysis	ENA https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/	Reports: electronic.

7	Local storage server with regular backups to an off-site location.	no specialized software is used, we just use a structure of file directories to organize WGS raw data and some of the analysis outputs.	An in-house workflow for quality control and genome assembly (FastQC + Trimmomatic + SPAdes + QUAST + bwa + QualiMap + MultiQC) Ridom SeqSphere+ for MLST and cgMLST-based investigations (assembled genomes are imported from the <i>in-house</i> workflow described previously) For Yersinia, we use the public Enterobase platform to perform allele-based analysis (MLST and cgMLST) ResFinder and RGI (with their respective databases) for AMR typing ABRicate and Virulence Factors Data Base for virulence profiling	Not all WGS data is uploaded publicly. At the moment, we only upload raw sequence data (fastq) to the European Nucleotide Archive when it is required by the project within which the data was generated. Apart from that, all analysis results and genotypes are automatically made public when Enterobase platform is used for data analysis.	The form of communication is determined on a case-by-case basis. We have not yet implemented a unified form of results communication for WGS-based investigations, this is a work in progress.
8	Internal server capacity i.c.w. server capacity from SURF SARA (https://userinfo.surfsara.nl/)	IBM Spectrum LSF, iRODS, Ridom Seqsphere +	Ridom Seqsphere + for in house target schemes and official cgMLST schemes. Various open source software packages (to many to mention here) implemented on an inhouse Linux server.	Yes, European Nucleotide Archive (ENA)	By email in results files (Excel etc)

pubMLST (*Campylobacter* and *Salmonella*, MLST), Ridom SeqSphere+: MLST, cgMLST, SeqSero (*Salmonella*), internal pipelines (serotype/serogroup: *E.coli* / *Shigella*, *Listeria*, *Yersinia*), own developed system in Linux called BacIL that uses free software's (for down sampling, trimming, assembly, quality check, contamination check, characterization, AMR and SNP-typing for *L. monocytogenes*, STEC, *Campylobacter* and *Salmonella*, Aries (Galaxy based from ISS EURL *E. coli*) for STEC (trimming, assembly, quality check, contamination check, characterization, and typing, DTU Centre for Genomic Epidemiology (characterization, typing), BactTyper (a naïve java application running on primarily bacterial WGS data, processing and managing a pipeline involving QC, assembly, classification and reporting. Reporting is then integrated into sql database for downstream access. visualization through SNPAnalyzer (in-house design, java based), NCBI BLAST (online), pubMLST (online), Pasteur MLST(online), Abricate (to detect AMR genes, virulence, OH antigens), Spades, Unicycler – Assemble data, Srst2- MLST types, Snippy- SNP distances, RaxML (phylogenetic trees), BRIG (plasmid genome analysis), an in-house workflow for quality control and genome assembly (FastQC + Trimmomatic + SPAdes + QUAST + bwa + QualiMap + MultiQC), Ridom SeqSphere+ for MLST and cgMLST-based investigations (assembled genomes are imported from the in-house workflow described previously for *Yersinia*), Enterobase platform to perform allele-based analysis (MLST and cgMLST), ResFinder and RGI (with their respective databases) for AMR typing, ABRicate and Virulence Factors Data Base for virulence profiling. The WGS data are uploaded to European Nucleotide Archive (ENA), Science Data, CERBERUS, ARIES, ECDC database, EFSA database, ENA, SRA (NCBI) and/or EpiPulse. The WGS results are communicated to ECDC, EpiNyt, Tessy, OIE, Exchange of files (e.g. Excel files), EpiPulse, national agencies (the data is sent in cloud-based or ftp-based systems), SmiLab (national), SmiNet (National), EPIS-ELDSNet/EpiPulse (EU) and/or EpisELDSnet.

Case Study: Management of antibiotic resistance data from Zoonosis monitoring (BfR-Germany)

A case study will help illustrate how data is managed and communicated. In Germany, AMR data is generated and/or collated in the regional laboratories and stored using the laboratory information and management system (LIMS). This data is then communicated to the German Federal Institute for Risk Assessment (BfR) using the MiBi-Portal (<https://mibi-portal.bfr.bund.de>). This portal automatically checks that all the required data fields are completed correctly and informs the personnel submitting the data if a revision is required. Any local revision of the data is imported and automatically updates the data in the regional LIMS. A LIMS is also used by BfR to store the AMR data (except NGS data) while Knime

(<https://www.knime.com/>) is used for data management and data analysis. Data is automatically extracted from the BfR LIMS by this open source tool, analysed and the output used in the preparation of graphs and tables in a transparent and standardised way. This analysis provides the information for the annual national zoonoses report and reports for each German Federal State, while an xml file is automatically generated which is directly included in the EFSA platform (<https://dcf.efsa.europa.eu/dcf-war/dc>).

3. Recommendations for a future Interoperable data management system

Armed with the information provided above it is now possible to suggest changes and develop a concept of how the laboratory testing, data management and communication should ideally be undertaken in the future.

3.1 Hardware and software harmonisation

The same types of hardware (eg. local server) and software (eg. LIMS) should be used in all laboratories (local, regional and national) across the EU. This system would ensure: [1] the data is secure; [2] the data is regularly backed up; [3] the file formats are consistent with those used in a central database located at regional, national and EU level; [4] the database is compliant with any laboratory accreditation requirements, and [5] the data is readily transferrable to these centralised databases without the requirement for additional resource input. Ideally the data stored in a local laboratory should be transferrable to regional, national and EFSA/ECDC at the click of a mouse.

Recommendation: EFSA/ECDC should evaluate the different software/information management systems available and recommend their use with a target harmonisation date of 2030. This will require a change in approach by governmental institutes that are very restricted by rules/procedures including the requirement to tender. The EFSA evaluation should be undertaken in full consultation with all relevant stakeholders and the long lead-in-time would allow laboratories to upgrade or replace their software when their current hardware and software licenses expire. As the same software will then be used across the EU it should be possible to negotiate a more favourable purchase or licensing arrangement which may be subsidised by DG Health. Alternatively the EC could purchase a pan-EU license or recommend the use of open access software. This approach is already used in the provision of recommended methods for testing. Such a centralised approach would facilitate compatibility in terms of data transfer and could result in the equivalent of a LIMS type system directly linking local laboratories with regional, national and European data centres. It is also consistent with

and could provide an additional function of the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC), which provides an environment for hosting and processing data to support EU science.

3.2. Reporting requirements and lost data

Indeed it is the ambition of the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) to provide European researchers, innovators, companies and citizens with a federated and open multi-disciplinary environment where they can publish, find and re-use data, tools and services for research, innovation and educational purposes. Zoonoses data would considerably enhance this offering. Some laboratories report to regional or national entities who in turn transfer this data/information to EFSA or ECDC, as required under current regulatory requirements. The limited amount of data that is legally required to be reported and the amount of work involved in current reporting systems has resulted in a considerable amount of valuable data remaining in local laboratories.

Recommendation: ECDC and EFSA should review and revise current reporting requirements. This should include a comprehensive review of all the data (eg. genotyping, NGS, virulence gene profiles, AMR, etc.) generated in the different laboratories across the EU to identify specific data that is and/or will be required to provide the scientific basis for future reports, opinions, etc. that underpin EC food safety and public health protection guidance, policy and legislation. Once this exercise is completed, it is essential that EFSA and ECDC have direct access to this data either through revised reporting requirements and/or the establishment of new information pipelines/networks and a central data hub. The provision of additional data could commence on a voluntary basis with a view to broadening the current regulatory reporting mandate once a central hub and data transfer system is established.

3.3 A central data hub

A central data hub is a critical part of any data management infrastructure and would provide secure data storage, restricted access, a validation function (that ensures data are from a reliable source and accurate), the ability to tag data appropriately for organisation (eg. STEC in beef) and a search function by target pathogen/hazard and by sample type (including sub-categories, eg 'Food-Meat-Beef-Ground beef').

Recommendation: ECDC and EFSA should develop a central data hub or database(s) to store the range of different data generated in the target laboratories in the EU. This should have the capacity to accommodate the different types of data including WGS data and be designed with a range of data usage in mind including data for annual zoonoses publications;

to inform risk assessment/policy development, inbuilt trend analysis and early warning system, etc. Such a data management system would have to be monitored and regularly audited with a view to ensuring the components remain up-to-date and capable of efficiently performing these functions. This EU Central Hub could also serve as a repository for the most up-to-date methods (as recommended by the EURLs) and as a communication platform between all the stakeholders.

4. Conclusion

Based on the data gathered in the questionnaires valuable data is being generated in the many laboratories testing human, animal, food, feed and environmental isolates throughout the EU. While the NRLs ensure aspects such as the methodologies being used are up-to-date, data storage and communication deficits mean the data generated is often not available to support key functions such as food safety policy development. Harmonised hardware and software usage, updated reporting requirements and the development of an EU central data hub would address these deficits and ensure European citizens get the maximum benefit from their considerable investment in laboratory testing across the EU.

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